
Expanding the Use of Electronic Materials and Guides for Improvement and Competency (E-MAGIC) Program to Increase the Percentage of Independent Readers of Grade 6 Class in Palandok ES

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Abstract

The main goal of this action research is to increase the percentage of independent readers of Grade 6 Class in Palandok Elementary School for the school year 2021-2022. It is about 36% of struggling readers were identified after the Pre-test in Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) was being conducted. The researchers aimed to increase the percentage of independent readers of Grade 6 Class through expanding the use of Electronic Materials and Guides for Improvement and Competency (E-MAGIC) Program.

Consequently, the result of this study showed that the percentage of independent readers is increased to 10% after the Post test in PHIL-IRI was administered. There is a significant improvement between the results of two test after the innovation was implemented through expanding the use of Electronic Materials and Guides for Improvement and Competency (E-MAGIC).

Hence, it is best recommended to teachers to regularly conduct a reading assessment to identify the frustration and struggling readers and take always an action to solve the problem through initiatives like E-MAGIC Program. In addition to this, teachers should make their localize video reading tutorial clips with explicit instructions so that the pupils can easily understand and grasp the lesson very well. Also, the support of the parents in this innovation take a great part in overcoming struggles of their children's performance in reading.

Keywords: reading, video-based learning, electronic platforms, face to face engagement

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Introduction

Quality education leads to progress and empowerment. It fights against ignorance and poverty. Good and quality education is a significant aspiration of the Department of Education despite of all the challenges that we are combatting right now. Amidst Covid19 threats, the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) of the Department of Education is continue to pursue its vision and mission. Strengthening this goal needs more applicable mode of learning delivery to adapt the educational system in the new normal.

Evidently, the learners performance is quite affected during this phase due to the absence of face-to-face interaction between the teachers and the pupils. The quality of learning environment of pupils and their habit of adopting the new design of teaching and learning process can also be a factor to a low academic performance and reading problem.

Reading is one of the most important skills which can help learners acquire, relay, and receive information. It can also help develop one's vocabulary in speaking, writing and listening. Learning to read is an essential part being taught in basic education. If a child fails to develop his reading ability, he might find problems in comprehension, become unresponsive to reading activities and lack of interest to learn in other areas.

In view of this, it is about 36% out of 56 pupils of Grade 6 class in Palandok Elementary School were identified as struggling readers after the Pre-test in Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) was being administered. The pupils were diagnosed to have a difficulty in recognizing basic sight words and have a poor reading ability.

Therefore, Palandok Elementary School has innovated and utilized a modern and standard program to aid this problem among struggling readers. The Electronic Materials and Guides for Improvement and Competency (E-MAGIC) program substitutes the presence of the teacher in teaching reading yet promotes the development in reading at home anytime.

The identified struggling readers are given an E-MAGIC package with inclusivity of video reading tutorial clips like basic sight words, phrases, sentences and story compilation.

In relation with this, because of the limited face-to-face classes, this E-MAGIC package serves as an access for video reading class at home that can be played anytime through their Led TVs, smart phones, laptops, CDs and other electronic gadgets.

Hence, it is best recommended to teachers to prepare and make their localize video reading tutorial clips and printed reading materials with explicit instructions. The easier the guides and directions in reading are, the effective and productive the results will be. Also engaging parents in this innovation give a strong partnership with the teachers and bridging the link towards their children's struggles in reading which promotes improvement and competency in reading performance of the Grade 6 class in Palandok Elementary School.

To foster quality education in the new normal especially in reading development, the learners should be provided with adequate and quality resources in and outside the traditional learning environment. To mention a few, is the availability of learning materials like books, printed reading materials and more.

The E-MAGIC program is also a unique approach that could possibly add to the list of the learning resources and results to positive outcome for the struggling readers. The recipient of this program could find ease and build self-confidence to learn reading

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effectively in an easy and comfortable way. Almaleki, Alhajaji and Alharbi (2021) cited in their study the effectiveness of interactions with the pupils to electronic platform in learning resulting to high level of motivation to learn. Thus, active participation and engagement of the different activities in the E-MAGIC package will promote effectively in breaking down struggles in reading.

Considerably, to switch on to modern platform like online lesson and the use of videos in learning will associate to productive way of learning among pupils (Hew, Jia and Bai 2021). Hence, this gives a chance to some learners who have difficulty to speed-up their skills inside the learning niche and to gradually open their doors for improvement.

Thus, in the absence of face-to-face engagement during the pandemic, the learners should still be on the track of progress through utilizing applicable, accessible and user – friendly electronic learning materials that is beneficial to learners (Legaspi, 2021). The E-MAGIC package is considered as digital materials suitably made for struggling readers. Digitalization of reading materials will provide great possibility for students to engage more and learn more in this time (Manila Standard Digital, 2021).

Accordingly, Vecchiato (2021) found out in his study that video-based learning instructions helps students understand complex topics. Through this electronic-based initiative, reading levels and instructions can be learned more thru audio-visual presentations. Therefore, the expansion and utilization of E-MAGIC program supports and provides opportunity for struggling readers to be more confident in improving their skills in reading.

This E-MAGIC program is a suitable and digestible to struggling readers in breaking the barriers in reading. Along with the printed reading materials, this innovation helps develop one's desire and interest to learn best in reading through videos. Simple model of video reading tutorial clips which are purposively made by the concern grade level teachers promotes sincere advocacy to hone pupils' reading ability. The E-MAGIC Package is composed of reading levels orderly. It has an explicit directions to simply guide the struggling readers to better understand each levels of the clips. The package can be shared through digital platforms and smartphones that can be viewed repeatedly at home anytime.

Research Questions

This action research will be conducted to increase the independent readers of Grade 6 class in Palandok ES through E-MAGIC program. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions.

1. What is the level of reading performance of Grade 6 Class in Pre-Reading Assessment?
2. What is the level of reading performance of Grade 6 Class in Post-Reading Assessment?
3. Is there a significant improvement between the levels of reading performance of Grade 6 Class in Palandok Elementary School after the E-MAGIC is implemented?

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Methodology

The participants of this study are the two sections of Grade 6 class in Palandok Elementary School. Both the Grade 6 section Azalea and Cattleya are composed of 28 respondents respectively. The Grade 6 Azalea will utilize a printed reading material while the Grade 6 Cattleya will use the printed reading materials along with the E-MAGIC Program.

The obtained data of this action research, the researcher may present an action research to the District Research Committee for possible adoption of strategy/techniques employed. A sampling design is purposively given and administered to the respondents to determine the level of reading performance.

Thereby, the concern grade level teachers will provide the E-MAGIC package to the treatment group and monitor the progress of the learners.

Hence, after the period of implementation, the data should be tested and analyzed whether it is effective or not.

This study use a descriptive and quantitative research design applying pre-test and post-test reading through Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) standard tool to determine the level of reading performance of the Grade 6 class in Palandok Elementary School.

The following are treated:

1. The level of reading performance in pre and post-reading assessment
2. The significant improvement of the reading performance of the pupils after the E-MAGIC Program is implemented through PHIL-IRI assessment tool.
3. The impact of E-MAGIC Program to the reading performance of the Grade 6 Class in Palandok ES.

Results and Discussions

The following data is the discussion of results and reflection of this study. The action research questions are presented through the collected data according to the results of the Pre and Post Reading Assessment of Grade 6 Class and were being evaluated and analyzed.

Question 1. What is the level of Reading Performance of Grade 6 Class in Pre-Reading Assessment?

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Table 1

PHIL-IRI ORAL READING ASSESSMENT RESULT FOR GRADE 6 AZALEA (CONTROL GROUP) AND GRADE 6 CATTLEYA (TREATMENT GROUP)

(Prefest)

Word Recognition Level	(Control Group) Frequency	Percentage	(Treatment Group) Frequency	Percentage
Independent	12	43%	7	25%
Instructional	6	21%	11	39%
Frustration	10	36%	10	36%
•Slow	3	30%	5	50%
•Syllable	4	40%	3	30%
•At Risk	3	30%	2	20%
TOTAL	28	100	28	100

The table 1 shows the level of reading performance during the Pre- Reading Assessment of Grade 6 Azalea (Control Group) where out of 28 pupils there are 12 or 43% are Independent Readers, 6 or 21% are Instructional and 10 or 36% are Frustration. Under Frustration Level, 3 are slow readers, 4 are syllabic readers and 3 pupils are at risk.

On the other hand, the results show the level of reading performance of Grade 6 Cattleya (Treatment Group) where out of 28 pupils there are 7 or 25% are Independent Readers, 11 or 39% are Instructional and 10 or 36% are Frustration Readers. There are 5 slow readers, 3 are syllabic readers and 2 are at risk who belong to Frustration Level.

Consequently, based on the results, 20 or 36% of the Grade 6 pupils are struggling readers that need to be addressed to increase the percentage of the reading performance of the Grade 6 Class in Palandok Elementary School.

Question 2. What is the level of Reading Performance of Grade 6 Class in Post-Reading Assessment?

Table 2

PHIL-IRI ORAL READING ASSESSMENT RESULT FOR GRADE 6 AZALEA (CONTROL GROUP) AND GRADE 6 CATTLEYA (TREATMENT GROUP)

(Posttest)

Word Recognition Level	(Control Group) Frequency	Percentage	(Treatment Group) Frequency	Percentage
Independent	14	50%	18	64%
Instructional	7	25%	8	29%
Frustration	7	25%	2	7%
•Slow	6	86%	2	100%
•Syllable	1	14%	0	0%

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●At Risk	0	0%	0	0%
TOTAL	28	100	28	100

The table 2 shows the level of Reading Performance of Grade 6 Azalea (Control Group) and Grade 6 Cattleya (Treatment Group) during the Post Reading Assessment.

The data based on the result of Post Reading Assessment for Printed Reading Materials or the Control Group shows that there are 14 or 50% are Independent readers, 7 or 25% are Instructional and 7 or 25% are Frustration readers. There are 6 slow readers, 1 syllabic reader and no pupil is at risk.

On the other hand, the result of Post Reading Assessment for Printed Reading Materials and E-MAGIC Program or the Experimental/Treatment Group revealed that out of 28 pupils, 18 or 64% are Independent readers, 8 or 29% are Instructional and 4 are belong to Frustration. It further shows that under Frustration level, 2 are slow readers while there are no pupils who are syllabic readers and at-risk.

Question 3. Is there a significant improvement between the levels of reading performance of Grade 6 Class in Palandok Elementary School after the E-MAGIC is implemented?

**Table 3
PHIL-IRI ORAL READING ASSESSMENT RESULT FOR GRADE 6 AZALEA (CONTROL GROUP) AND GRADE 6 CATTLEYA (TREATMENT GROUP)**

(Results in Pretest and Posttest)

Word Recognition Level	Pre-test (Control Group) Frequency	Percentage	Posttest (Control Group) Frequency	Percentage	Pre-test (Treatment Group) Frequency	Percentage	Posttest (Treatment Group) Frequency	Percentage
Independent	12	43%	14	50%	7	25%	18	64%
Instructional	6	21%	7	25%	11	39%	8	29%
Frustration	10	36%	7	25%	10	36%	2	7%
●Slow	3	30%	6	86%	5	50%	2	100%
●Syllable	4	40%	1	14%	3	30%	0	0%
●At Risk	3	30%	0	0%	2	20%	0	0%
TOTAL	28	100	28	100	28	100	28	100

Table 3 shows the significant improvement between the levels of Reading Performance of Grade 6 section Azalea (Control Group) and Grade 6 Cattleya (Treatment Group) after the implementation of the program.

Accordingly, the data shows that Grade 6 Azalea which utilized the Printed Reading Materials is increased to 7% of its Independent readers while the Grade 6 Cattleya which used the Printed Reading Materials and E-MAGIC Program is increased to 39% of its Independent readers. In addition to, the percentage of Frustration readers in Grade 6 Azalea is decreased from 36% to 25% or from 10 it becomes 7 while the Frustration readers in Grade 6 Cattleya is decreased from 36% to 7% approximately or from 10 down to 2.

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Findings

The following findings were revealed:

1. Almost one-third of the Grade 6 pupils are identified struggling and under Frustration Level where some of them are slow readers, syllabic and at-risk.
2. The two sections of Grade 6 Class in Palandok Elementary School utilized two reading innovations to support and address the existing problems in reading. The Grade 6 Azalea being the Control Group constituted the Printed Reading Materials while the Grade 6 Cattleya as the Experimental/Treatment Group used the Printed Reading Materials and Electronic Materials and Guides for Improvement and Competency (E-MAGIC) Program.
3. After the administration of the reading assessment, the reading performance of two sections show a substantial difference. Based on the data gathered, the use of Printed Reading Materials and E-MAGIC Program has 32% more effective than the use of Printed Reading Materials alone. The independent readers in Grade 6 Cattleya is increased to 39% while the Grade 6 Azalea is leveled up to 7% only.
4. The implementation of the E-MAGIC Program has a significant improvement to the reading performance of the Grade 6 Class in Palandok Elementary School.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drive at:

1. Adopting the new and modern ways in reading development among frustration and struggling readers are less likely hassle and complicated yet effective in reading development.
2. The E-MAGIC Program promotes easy and comfortable way in learning to read at home anytime.
3. Continuous administration and tracking the reading progress of pupils leads to increase the baseline in creating more initiatives for pupils' reading mastery and development.
4. Follow up or reading monitoring in school regarding the lessons in the E-MAGIC Package provides the opportunity for the struggling readers to be assessed what they have learned at home.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions made, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. Since the E-MAGIC is found effective in teaching reading and promotes reading performance among struggling readers, this new innovation should be used in reading remediation.

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2. Teachers should prepare their localized video reading tutorial clips with explicit instructions.
3. Regular reading assessment is highly encouraged to identify the pupils who need most of our assistance and will be given a tailored fit intervention.

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